

Analyst Administrator
Date Tuesday, May 17, 2022 11:48 AM

Sample Name	Description	Quality Checks
CAS-119-4 crystals_1	Sample 024 By Administrator Date Tuesday, May 17 2022	The Quality Checks give rise to a Weak Bands warning for the sample.